

Creative Learning

by Parham Izadyar

what is creative learning? and why is it important?

we, humans are curious creatures by nature, after our basic needs we seek answers to our questions. therefore, we learn, to be able to find these answers. but first we must have questions. otherwise, what are we learning for? without having question, without curiosity, creativity, imagination "learning" is more like pointless transfer of information and techniques. "creative-learning" is having questions and seeking the answers in a creative way. being curious about what happens, why and how. We all have these qualities within us, just like when we were children, we were full of questions: what is this? what is that? why sky is blue? how animals communicate without words? we still have our own questions in a different level. but not always consciously. in some circumstances we just don't pay attention.

somehow in Iran (and perhaps in many places) we have lost that inquisitive spirit more than usual. the empty place for "creative learning" is felt in Iran specially in music field. sometimes it felt in educational system and sometimes inside us. it is a common issue that we feel asking creative questions is unpolite. Although, the feedback for our curiosity is not always nice but it doesn't mean expressing them is wrong or unpolite.

it's sad to see students just do what their teacher asked them to do. or they go to their teachers and ask for homework. and never ask for creative activities. even if they do, it's not welcomed by some teachers. unfortunately, creativity is forbidden in our educational system. of course, we have good teachers who inspire us to be creative, but when they try to do it in public classes, it won't be accepted by the system or society. so, it's not only educational system it's like a darkness in our culture, or the dominant part of it. even if we have interest for creativity, we have to express it in a private place.

so, it's not surprising that the only way we know for learning is following the rules. the absence of this "creative learning" is why most of musicians don't volunteer for artistic activities. or most of composers stop composing after graduation from university. they don't know "creative-learning" they don't know how to be curious and have ideas, how to find their own questions about a piece.

questions like: *what if 'this' part of the piece changes to something else? if the composer wanted to convey the certain concept, why did he/she use these methods? how is the performer's relationship with the piece? what was the first impression of performer about this piece? why these instruments are chosen by composer? what if these notes are played in reverse? how this idea cross the composer's mind at the first place? how come this piece is so impressive?* and so on.

of course, these questions are not general, the whole point is to have your own questions.

because of the bad educational system and bad habits in our culture we only know how to compose as a composer. how to play instruments as an instrumentalist. How to perform as a performer. but we don't create situations for presentation or collaborations. we don't start conversations, we only reply. we don't ask questions, we only answer. we don't invite people, we only wait for invitation. we don't do something new, we only do what we already know.

In order for "creative learning" will be formed in us, it needs awareness, importance, practice, time and energy. so first we have to know such way of learning exists, and how much we need it, then read more about it and practice. it's hard to change things like these but every step is precious.

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